

“Built by CDH” Software Warranty and *“Built by CDH” Long Term Service Agreement* document Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton (hereafter CDH) commitment to and responsibilities for maintaining and supporting applications developed by the CDH Development & Design Team. These documents also spell out corresponding Project Director (PI) responsibilities toward the same goal, as well as the conditions under which a project will no longer be maintained by CDH, including the possibility that a site may eventually be archived and turned off, should it become unmaintainable or a security risk.

Maintenance plans are based on infrastructure provided by Princeton University Office of Information Technology (OIT), which provides Virtual Server hosting to faculty and departments with no cost or annual fee.

Cite this document:

Bauer, Jean, and Rebecca Sutton Koeser. *“Built by CDH” Software Warranty*. Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton. 2018. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3359198>

“Built by CDH” Software Warranty

This document outlines the warranty CDH places on launched projects built by the Development and Design Team under a project charter and housed on Princeton servers.

The “Built by CDH” warranty goes into effect one week after the project launches. Any problems in the first week will be dealt with immediately to ensure a smooth initial launch.

The warranty period lasts for 3 months or 12 story points (roughly equivalent to the development work of a full two-week iteration), whichever comes first. During the warranty period, CDH will fix bugs that impact core site functionality found under real world conditions. This story point limit does not include any major security patches required during the warranty period. Following successful testing, the PI will receive an update on how many story points remain in the warranty.

While the project is under warranty, the PI must respond to all questions within a timeframe of one week, depending on the severity of the issue. Deadlines for response will be included in all communications with the PIs.

Also during warranty, all bug fixes and updates must be tested within one week. Deadlines will be included in all communications requiring testing.

If the PI fails to respond to questions or the features are not tested by the deadline, then the warranty is void. Project will be put onto the Long Term Service Agreement.

Questions about the warranty should be directed to CDH’s Lead Developer.